

Quantum Mechanics Retains Precise Position Information in Steady State Scenarios?

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Quantum mechanics is usually associated with loss of spatial information. For example, in the case of a superposition $\sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$, one has the Heisenberg uncertainty relation (standard deviation x) * (standard deviation p) $\geq \hbar/2$ and even in the case of a precise p , the probability $\exp(ipx)$ suggests an impulse hit can occur within $dx = \hbar/p$.

We suggest here, however, that there exists an example in which quantum mechanics retains precise spatial information even in the case in which classical mechanics does not. In particular, we consider the situation of a $dx = \hbar/p = 1$ (i.e. in units of 2×3.14) and a one dimensional set of creation points for a particle: $x=0, x=1/3, x=2/3$. In such a case, the phase shift of each $\exp(ipx + \text{phase shift})$ will identify the precise position (or pretty close if one considers the notion of a wavepacket) of the creation point in a steady stream scenario. In a classical situation, a steady stream scenario will completely wash out any information of the creation points of the particles as there is no distinguishing them in time. If one wishes to consider all different kinds of x creation points, then different p values are required. Thus, discerning space implies a loss of precise information of p .

The Importance of Phase in $\exp(ipx)$

Classical mechanics describes interactions in terms of p (momentum) and energy (E), but one also follows a particle deterministically through $x(t)$. We have argued in previous notes that at some length scale, one cannot predict an elastic collision deterministically and that all one may say is that momentum and energy are conserved and that given an initial e_1, e_2 and p_1, p_2 (vectors in 1-dimension), one must assign a probability to the outcomes. Given no special information, the product of outcomes should be a uniform distribution, so:

$$p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_k)p(e_l) \text{ for } e_1+e_2 = e_i+e_j = e_k+e_l \text{ ((1a)) and}$$

$$p(p_1)p(p_2) = p(p_i)p(p_j) = p(p_k)p(p_l) \text{ for } p_1+p_2 = p_i+p_j + p_k+p_l \text{ ((1b))}$$

Here all p 's are vectors in the same direction. Furthermore, for free particles, there is no distributed variable that would yield a real-value probability and so we consider:

$$\exp(i C_1 e) \text{ and } \exp(i C_2 p) \text{ ((2))}$$

$$\text{To make this Lorentz invariant, one has } \exp(-iEt+px) \text{ ((3))}$$

This means that there is inherent uncertainty in x and t for an interaction, i.e.

$$dx = \hbar/p \text{ and } dt = \hbar/e \text{ ((4))}$$

As a result, quantum mechanics is thought of in terms of losing precise information about x and t even if one has a precise e and p . (In some cases in the literature, a wavepacket $\sum a(p)\exp(ipx) \exp(-iet)$ is used to describe a free particle and so there is a standard deviation for p and x , but the wavepacket spreads in space in time and this is unphysical, so we consider $\exp(ipx)$ for a free particle in this note.)

We suggest that it is not enough to simply use ((4)) to describe a moving particle, but that one needs the cycling probability $\exp(-iet) \exp(ipx)$ which displays these dx and dt values. In other words, one cannot think of a dx translating together with a center-of-mass of the particle, with a uniform distribution within this dx . This would involve probability disappearing from the back end of dx and suddenly appearing at the front. The probability seems to display a kind of dynamical property of its own. This means it is possible to have to have particles with the same p be out of phase if they are created at different x points, i.e. x_1 and x_2 , yielding $\exp(ipx_1)$ and $\exp(ipx_2)$. As a result, with a dynamical $\exp(ipx)$ and not simply a dx attached to the center-of-mass, one may possibly pinpoint the creation point of the particle.

One might argue that in Newtonian mechanics, different creation points for the same p with the same rest mass m_0 yield the velocity v and so the particles arrive at a certain destination at different times and are discerned in this way. Such is not the case with a steady stream which removes the distinction of time. In the quantum case, however, one may still possibly discern the creation point due to the phase shift in the following manner.

We consider particles with the same m_0 and p , such that $dx = \hbar/p$ equals an integer number, say 1 (i.e. $2 \cdot 3.14$ for the sake of argument). One may then place creation points at $x=0$, $x=1/3$ and $x=2/3$ and each will have different phase shifts from $x=0$. From $x=2/3$ to the destination, the phase of all is the same. As a result, measuring the phase shifts (through interference) allows one to determine the creation points even if one has a steady state situation. One may note that in this example, if one had placed creation points at $x=4/3$ and $7/3$ that these would have given a phase shift equal to that of $x=1/3$ as 1 maps to $2 \cdot 3.14$ and disappears. Thus, a single p cannot be used to determine all creation points.

In general, one would need to use a variety of different values of p in order to discern more and more x creation points. Thus, increasing knowledge of all x creation points means reducing precise knowledge of p .

Conclusion

In conclusion, given $dx = \hbar/p$ and $(\text{standard deviation } p) \cdot (\text{standard deviation } x) \geq \hbar/2$, quantum mechanics is seen as a theory which causes one to lose deterministic information, i.e. precise information about position, as an example. We suggest, however, that one must introduce a precise position value when using $\exp(ipx)$ to describe a free particle. In other words, one is not simply concerned with the uncertain region $dx = \hbar/p$, but also of the precise starting point for $\exp(ipx)$ (here $x=0$). There are two values of concern, a spread of x and a precise x starting point. We suggest that quantum mechanics makes use of both.

(We do not use a wavepacket because it spreads out in x in time.). In particular, $\exp(ipx)$ is a dynamic probability which creates $dx = \hbar/p$ as one moves through x . One does not simply

have dx attached to the center-of-mass point which follows $x=vt$. As a result, dx is linked to the creation point of the particle and different creation points may be out of phase. We give the example of $dx=1$ (in $2\sqrt{3}$ units) and consider creation points at $x=0$, $x=1/3$ and $x=2/3$. In such a case, a single $p = \hbar k$ can discern the three creation points (through interference) in a steady state scenario for which Newtonian mechanics cannot. If one wishes to discern more x creation points, it seems that one needs to use different p 's. In other words, as x creation point discernment improves, one needs more p values and so no longer has sharp p information.